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Wind Energy and Sustainable Development in Ahilayanagar District

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Abstract

Energy is prime need of human being. Man has made his social and economic evolution with the help of different kinds of energy resources. In his primitive stages of evolution he does not know about heat energy. Man has made uses different kinds of energy resources as wood, coal, thermal energy, electrical energy, thermal energy, biogas energy, atomic energy, solar and wind energy, wind energy is generate with the help of wind velocity. Wind energy resources are renewable source of energy. It is clean source of energy. At the global level it has more scope. From the past history of human history man is using this energy for different kinds of economic activity. In desert region it has more ability. India is a tropical country that's why; it has large scope for the generation of electricity and rural development. Today in this district, there five working sites. These sites are generating 470 Mw electricity. Due to the Ahilyanagar district physiography and climatic condition, it has more sixteen sites as kolegon, Khandke, Kavada dongar, Pimpalgon Kavada, Sirsgaon, Pachpatta, Kurkundi, Kisegavan, Gulewadi, and other high platform of this district. These wind farms has made sustainable development in this geographical region as energy supply for the remote area. This energy is a clean source of electricity; Wind energy has taken much part in supply of electricity. It has ability to stop the global warring issues. This energy is sources of renewable energy that's why it has more scope in national development policy, Wind energy is part of science and technology, that's why it is a part of innovation. With the help of wind energy it is possible for tourism development activity. With the help of renewable energy resources it is possible for the regional planning in this district. There is greater role for domestic lighting and social justice for the rural region with the help of wind energy in Ahilyanagar district, this research paper, researcher has study about historical review about the wind energy at global and national level.

Key Word : Wind Energy, Sustainable development, Wind Turbine, Wind Farm, Environment, Electricity Grid, Wind velocity, Rural Development, Conservation of Soil,

Introduction:

Man is active animal on the earth surface. For the purpose of more work in the simple energy, he had made lot of simple machine. Leaver is a best example for it. This aactivity is useful in regular life. Man has modified this energy resources form the past period time to time as the wood, coal, petroleum, natural gasses, electricity and nuclear energy. Among these resources electricity has more efficiency. Electricity is most impotent sources of energy in world. There are number of sources for generation of electricity. Coal is one of important crud resources in the thermal power plant. In this thermal plant coal is burn and electricity is generated. These thermal plants had made lot of pollution and it is one of agent in global warming which has made global climatic changes

Wind is horizontal movement of air. Wind flow from high pressure location toward the low pressure location. These high and low pressure location generated by uneven distribution of solar radiation. Temperature intensity of solar radiation generates high and low pressure location. For the purpose of pressure balances wind flows from high pressure to low pressure location. Wind has the motion it generate kinetic energy. This kinetic energy is important in number of field as rotation for simple machine. In case of wind electricity, wind velocity converts into mechanical energy and further for electricity. Wind electricity is a renewable energy, it is never ending. This is modern type non-conventional renewable type of energy resources. He also suggest how wind energy is useful for sustainable development.

History of Wind Energy:

There are number of references for wind energy in past history. In past history man was using wind velocity for the purpose of irrigation in agriculture activity as pumping water. The other domestic references are as gridding food grain. It was the simple machine. In modern period there was generate electricity by first time in Scotland made by Prof. James Blyth in 1891.

This was first design for turbine generation of electricity. There was circular spoke in this turbine wind mill. In India, development of electricity starts from December 1952. This project was developed by CSIR. Today in India, there is 50,000Mw. Electricity generated by wind energy resources. The major production states are Tamilnadu, Maharashtra, Gujarat, Karnataka and Rajasthan. Maharashtra state is generating wind electricity is 5500 Mw. State nodal agency for wind energy research is Maharashtra Energy Development Agency (MEDA). In this state major wind turbine company are Suzlon,, Vesta, Gamesa, RrGen, Letner and Shriram manufacturing company. Today there is very high developed technology has made new construction for wind turbine. These wind turbine has fixed with computer technology. Due to the high capacity baring these wind turbine can be generate electricity even low velocity of the wind. The wind turbine is also small size or huge size. Small or micro size wind turbine is useful for the domestic utility of electricity. As per its demand, these wind turbines can be develop electricity in desert, mountain and coastal region. As per todays need it has mechanized with different kind of technology.

Wind Energy in Ahmednagar District:

Ahilyanagar district is largest district of Maharashtra state. As physiographic condition of this state is basalt rock made by volcanic igneous rock. Geographical latitudinal location of this district is 18⁰ 20' N to 19⁰59' north and longitudinal reference is 73⁰40'E to 75⁰43' East. This site of location in the western ghat Sahyadries ranges of the Balaghat Mountain. As a climatic view, It is tropical climate. It has suitable for wind velocity and other climatic condition for wind turbine. Due to the physiographic and climatic condition there six wind farms are generating 500 Mw. electricity. Wind electricity generation of is started from the 1999. This district is located in Balaght mountain region. Its physiography and climatic condition is ideal for generation of electricity. Nation Wind Energy Institute has suggested for more site in energy development. In coming period, This sites will be generate more electricity and that will be applied for technical employment. Today there are six wind farms are generating the electricity as – Kavada Dongar, Khandke, Daula Wadgaon, Pachpatta, Kuslum and Nadur Pathar. Following table shows the wind farm in this district.

No.	Name of Wind farm	Number of Turbine	Generation of Electricity Mw.
1.	Kavda Dongar (Supa)	63	64. 500
2.	Khandke (Mehekari)	192	153.600
3.	Dula Wadgaon	35	70. 000
4.	Pachpatta	146	138. 950
5.	Kuslum (Sawatada)	23	13. 500
6.	Nandur Pathar	12	29. 700
Total		471	470.55 Mw.

Source: Composed by Researcher

Sources: Composed by Researcher

Due to Physiographical condition of this region, National Intitule of Wind Energy, Chennai (NIWE) has Suggested potential sixteen sites – Kolegaon, Khanke, Kavada Dongar, Pimpalgaon Kavada, Sirsgaon, Pachpatta, Kurkundi,

Kosegavan, Gulwadi, Khanur Pathar, Mahinda, Wadgaon Savtal, Dolasne, Saargaon Peth, Savalavihir and Drodi. These potential sites are considered with references of wind velocity, density and height for geographical location.

There are more suitable sites for generation of electricity from the minor local places. With the help of these wind energy, it has possible more regional development. Wind energy will also play a role in the regional planning and economic balancing in this district.

Role of Wind Energy in Sustainable Development:

Wind energy is a source of clean energy. It is a renewable source of energy. This energy has more capacity as a energy resource. We can use this energy continuously whole day and night time. This energy is not harmful for environment. Wind energy has the following importance in the rural sustainable development.

1. This energy is generating in remote hilly area. It will lead for rural and remote area. Local need of electricity in remote area will be fulfilled by this wind energy. This remote area may be mountain, forest, coastal or desert.
2. Wind energy does not need of external sources of fuel. These wind turbines are more efficient than other sources of electricity. Even in a small wind velocity, these wind mills generate more electricity. This wind turbine can generate electricity at day and night time, In India it has more efficiency in summer and monsoon period. In modern period, mechanical and computer technology has developed more efficient and high capacity wind turbine. Some of the wind turbines are more than 5 Mw. capacities.
3. Total demand of this district electricity is 700 Mw. Day by day demand of electrical energy is going more demand. This wind electricity has capacity to fulfill the necessity of the district. This electricity will be useful in industrial sector, irrigation purpose, urban and domestic purpose. This local wind electricity would have more capacity to supply energy for rural development and planning programme.
4. Thermal electrical power plant had made more environmental pollution by burning of the coal as a fuel. It is one of major causes of global warming. Wind energy is source of green energy.
5. Wind Energy is a renewable non-conventional source of electricity. It has more capacity for generation of energy, The other sources as coal and petroleum are non-cyclic sources, For this views, wind energy is best option for coal and petroleum natural non cyclic energy resources.
6. With this wind energy farm it is possible for rural development. It will be made plantation and watershed program in the barren land.
7. Wind farm will be generating new innovation and technological attitude in remote rural area. Young generation will be aware about science and technology. Hence it will be create technological literacy in rural area.
8. This electricity will be made development in tourism and historical activity.
9. In a mountain region, wind electricity is applicable for agriculture irrigation activity.
10. This district is active in sugarcane industry. Wind electricity is useful with national electric grid system.
11. For rural domestic lighting there is more scope for wind electricity.

Conclusion:

Hence, wind energy is a source of electricity. It has more capacity to provide electricity for rural sustainable development. With the help of energy, it has possible for rural development. As an environmental view it is eco-friendly. Ahmednagar district had made the role model in sector of rural development. In coming period there is scope for wind energy in rural sustainable development.

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Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

References:

1. Literature Review of Wind Turbine: Zufer Usman, 2018
2. Potential of wind energy in India : Hossain j. 2011
3. Wind Farms in Rural Area: Munday M. 2011
4. Wind Energy a Clean Renewable Energy; Vasudev Salunkhe, 2018
5. Climate of Maharashtra, IMD Pune, 2014
6. Electricity Generation by sources: International Energy Agency, 2018
7. Evolution of Wind Energy : Mohaad Sritti, 2019
8. Geoinformatics Application in Rural Development: Kumar D.2015
9. The Use of Wind Energy In India :Mallet V.K. 2001.
10. Wind Energy Power: Brush C.F. 2008